

A Rawlsian Mixed Integer Programming Approach for Fair Classification

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Abstract. Binary classification is a common machine learning methodology that aims to partition data into two classes as accurately as possible. One major drawback of these methods is that they are prone to producing unfair results. One real-life example of this is the Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions algorithm, which was designed to label individuals as “low” or “high” risk for recidivism. The algorithm produced predictions that had significantly worse accuracy for individuals in one demographic group than in others. While many methods have been proposed to address this, they are known to sacrifice overall prediction accuracy for the whole population. We present a Rawlsian fairness approach that prioritizes algorithmic performance for the worst-off demographic group without sacrificing overall performance. We couple our Rawlsian fairness approach with a scoring system using a mixed integer programming (MIP) formulation. Our approach assigns a score to each individual and assigns them to a class if it is above or below a specific threshold. By using an MIP approach, we can solve for the optimal threshold rather than relying on the user to identify the threshold before executing the method. Our MIP approach is also flexible, as it provides the user with multiple ways to obtain sparse or integer solutions. Our results yield fair outcomes even when a particular group comprises a small proportion of the entire dataset and provide insight into how our methodology compares to other fairness approaches.

Key words: Rawlsian Fairness, Binary Classification, Mixed Integer Program

1. Introduction

Binary classification algorithms in machine learning categorize data into two different classes and are widely used with a broad array of applications, such as diagnosing diseases (Shreem et al. 2022), detecting fraud (Leevy et al. 2023), and predicting student performance (Zerouaoui and Idri 2022). Despite many advances in the study of binary classification algorithms, many of these algorithms are prone to producing unfair results in certain circumstances. A famous binary classification method is the Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions (COMPAS) algorithm (Angwin et al. 2022), which was designed to label individuals as “low-risk” or “high-risk” for recidivism. The algorithm had a significantly higher rate of incorrect predictions for black individuals than white ones. When an algorithm prioritizes the overall prediction accuracy across all individuals in the dataset, it could prioritize the prediction accuracy for members belonging to one demographic group over members in others as a result. Therefore, accuracy for the worst-off demographic group could be dramatically worse than for others.

There are many different ways to evaluate fairness with classification algorithms. A common notion of fairness is the assurance that individuals of different demographic groups are treated similarly. According to this idea, fairness can be enforced by defining a function that penalizes outcomes that result in large performance disparity across groups (Yue et al. 2023). Verma and

Rubin (2018) summarizes three of the most common fairness metrics used with classification algorithms: statistical parity, equal opportunity, and equalized odds. Statistical parity (Besse et al. 2022) ensures that subjects in different groups have an equal probability of receiving the same classification. Equal opportunity (Zhang and Bareinboim 2018) ensures that subjects in the positive class have the same probability of being classified incorrectly across different demographic groups. Equalized odds (Awasthi et al. 2020) ensures that the probabilities of being correctly and incorrectly assigned to the positive class are the same across all groups. Satisfying these fairness criteria often leads to significant deterioration of the classification's prediction accuracy. This phenomenon is known as the fairness-accuracy trade-off (Menon and Williamson 2018).

Unbalanced datasets present a challenge to producing fair results. These datasets have one class (majority class) that has significantly more entries than other classes (minority classes). Such datasets often yield unfair outcomes, as conventional classification algorithms tend to favor the majority class, relegating minority classes to noise. Consequently, during the training phase, the influence of minority classes is severely limited (Kumar et al. 2022). To address these issues, common approaches involve altering the data sampling for the algorithm. Random over-sampling (ROS) (Elreedy et al. 2024) involves sampling minority entries more frequently while under-sampling (RUS) (Liu and Tsoumakas 2020) reduces the frequency of majority entries. However, ROS can introduce additional noise due to the inclusion of extra samples, leading to overfitting. Conversely, RUS may remove crucial training data, resulting in underfitting.

To address the above challenges, we propose a Rawlsian (or "minimax") fairness approach based on Rawls (1999) to maximize the worst-off demographic group's performance. Our method does not alter the data in any way, so it is not exposed to the shortcomings of ROS and RUS. It mitigates the impact of unbalanced datasets on fairness by ensuring prediction accuracy is not compromised for any group regardless of how much of the dataset they comprise. Also, this methodology does not sacrifice error as much as the aforementioned fairness metrics do because it does not hinder performance for other demographic groups to achieve similar performance across all groups.

Rawlsian fairness has been considered in many applications such as supply-chain management (Shehadeh 2023), healthcare (Wang 2019), and resource allocation (Munguía-López and Ponce-Ortega 2021), and its implications are discussed in Hooker and Williams (2012). Rawlsian fairness with classification was considered in Hashimoto et al. (2018), which formulates a Rawlsian loss function, but they don't solve it directly, and only provide bounds for it. Shah et al. (2021) also considers a Rawlsian fairness model, but it is only solvable when second-order statistics are known. Martinez et al. (2021) also propose a Rawlsian fairness framework, however, they make more assumptions on the structure of the data compared to our method, which is more generalizable. Li et al. (2025) uses a Rawlsian approach, however it is applied to a different setting than ours. Their model is specifically designed to consider the case where demographic groups are unknown.

Fairness can be incorporated into classification algorithms through pre- or post-processing. Pre-processing methods adjust the data before feeding it into any classification algorithm (Calmon et al. 2017) while post-processing methods adjust the output of a classification algorithm (Hardt et al. 2016). These methods can lead to high variability with the ultimate performance error (Pessach and Shmueli 2022), or sub-optimal results (Woodworth et al. 2017). To avoid these shortcomings, we consider an in-processing method does not require any pre- or post-processing.

We combine our Rawlsian fairness approach with a classification method that uses a score function with a threshold. This common classification approach works by assigning a score to each data entry and then classifying them based on whether the score is above or below a certain threshold (Barocas et al. 2023). One issue with these methods is that the threshold is an input that must be decided by the user, and it is not obvious what threshold value will give the best result. Area under

the curve (AUC) (Calders and Jaroszewicz 2007) is another metric used for classification problems that evaluate a score function's ability to correctly classify data for all possible threshold values, and this metric has been explored with fairness considerations (Yang et al. 2025). Optimizing the AUC is robust to threshold selection since the user does not need to identify the best threshold. However, optimizing AUC considers thresholds that might lead to poor prediction accuracy. Furthermore, directly solving for the maximum AUC is difficult (Gao et al. 2013).

We consider a mixed integer program (MIP) formulation for our Rawlsian score function. There are a few examples of MIPs used for binary classification, such as Balvert (2024). However, their approach is used for a more specific context than ours since they only consider binary input data. We consider the Supersparse Linear Integer Model (SLIM), which is a MIP method that can solve classification problems while guaranteeing optimal balance between sparsity and error without the need for additional post-processing developed by Ustun et al. (2013). These methods directly provide the optimal threshold value as a model output rather than an input. Therefore, the burden of choosing the threshold value as an input before solving the model is alleviated (Zeng et al. 2017). Providing the optimal threshold value also alleviates the need to consider all possible thresholds simultaneously, as AUC optimization methods do. Another advantage is that these models allow the user to obtain integer coefficients, which improves interpretability. Integer coefficients could be more desirable than real coefficients in certain settings. For example, Ustun and Rudin (2016) describe how the interpretability provided by integer coefficients is desirable in a medical scoring system, where coefficients are used for disease diagnosis. Furthermore, a MIP framework provides modeling flexibility to adjust sparsity in different ways, either through penalization terms in the objective function, or through upper-bounding constraints (Ustun and Rudin 2016). We summarize this paper's contributions below. Our novel Rawlsian MIP provides the following:

1. fair classification results by prioritizing the worst-off group despite unbalanced data
2. the optimal threshold value as an output, so the user does not have to identify a threshold value before implementation and does not have to consider all possible thresholds simultaneously
3. flexibility to improve interpretability in multiple ways: including integer coefficients and incorporating sparsity through objective function penalization or an upper-bounding constraint

We introduce our model formulation in Section 2. In Section 3, we introduce the datasets and present experimental results. In Section 4, we conclude the paper.

2. Model Formulation

We begin this section by introducing notation used in our model. We then introduce the original loss function proposed by Ustun et al. (2013) that does not consider fairness to motivate our novel Rawlsian Loss Function. This loss function is non-linear and non-convex, so we present an approach to reformulate this problem into a tractable MIP.

2.1. Preliminaries

We consider a dataset with N entries with P features and K demographic groups. Our methodology prioritizes the worst-off group by aiming to ensure that none of the demographic groups $1, \dots, K$ suffer disparate classification error. $(1, x_1^i, \dots, x_p^i)$, is a feature vector for the i^{th} individual. y_i and $\hat{y}_i \in \{-1, 1\}$ are the true and predicted labels for individual i , respectively. The decision variable $\lambda = (\lambda_0, \dots, \lambda_p)$ is a vector of coefficients used to define a linear score function. ϵ is a small perturbation term, Λ is the maximum allowable value for λ , and M is a large number.

C_0 and C_1 are the respective penalty coefficients for L_0 and L_1 regularization terms in our objective. The L_0 norm of a vector λ is defined as $\|\lambda\|_0 := |\{i : \lambda_i \neq 0\}|$, or the number of indices with nonzero components. Therefore, by definition, reducing $\|\lambda\|_0$ through L_0 regularization directly

optimizes sparsity, but minimizing the L_0 norm is a non-convex problem (Ramirez et al. 2013). The L_1 norm is defined as $\|\lambda\|_1 := \sum_{i=1}^P |\lambda_i|$. Even though L_1 regularization does not directly optimize sparsity, combining it with L_0 regularization can improve variable selection and stability (Liu and Wu 2007). Furthermore, if the coefficients must be integer values, using L_1 regularization in addition to L_0 can ensure that the optimal coefficients are coprime integers (Ustun and Rudin 2014). Integer coefficients are desirable for linear scoring systems, which are commonly used in applications such as education (Guskey 2013) or healthcare (Knaus et al. 1991). By using a MIP framework, our formulation addresses the non-convexity of the L_0 norm and allows us to simultaneously minimize the L_0 and L_1 norms.

2.2. Original Loss Function

The original loss function used in Ustun et al. (2013) minimizes classification by minimizing the number of incorrect classifications, which is equivalent to maximizing classification accuracy. In other words, if $(x^i)^T \lambda > 0$ and $y_i = 1$ or $(x^i)^T \lambda < 0$ and $y_i = -1$, this is considered a correct classification. Otherwise, it is incorrect. Therefore, our loss function is:

$$\min_{\lambda \in \mathcal{X}} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{1}\{y_i(x^i)^T \lambda \leq 0\} + C_0 \|\lambda\|_0 + C_1 \|\lambda\|_1 \quad (1)$$

where $C_0 \|\lambda\|_0$ and $C_1 \|\lambda\|_1$ terms exist to penalize any λ with a large L_0 or L_1 norm, respectively. This loss function, however, does not incorporate any fairness. Here, \mathcal{X} is a set of feasible solutions, where $\mathcal{X} \in \{\mathbb{R}^{P+1}, \mathbb{Z}^{P+1}\}$. In other words, we allow λ to be a real or integer-valued $P+1$ -dimensional vector. $\mathbf{1}$ is an indicator function whose value is 1 if its input is true and 0 otherwise. The objective is to choose a λ to minimize the number of incorrect classifications. A classification, in this context, is determined by the sign of $(x^i)^T \lambda$. Formally, the classification approach follows:

$$\hat{y}_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (x^i)^T \lambda > 0 \\ -1 & \text{if } (x^i)^T \lambda \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

We denote the first element of λ as λ_0 . Because the first element of x is 1 for all i by definition, λ_0 adjusts the overall score function $(x^i)^T \lambda$ by a scalar. Therefore, λ_0^* acts as a threshold for the score function. This can be understood by observing the equivalent representation of (2):

$$\hat{y}_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \sum_{j=1}^P \lambda_j x_j^i \geq -\lambda_0 \\ -1 & \text{if } \sum_{j=1}^P \lambda_j x_j^i \leq -\lambda_0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

We aim to select λ_0 to maximize the amount of data points i assigned to class 1 if $\sum_{j=1}^P \lambda_j x_j^i \geq -\lambda_0$ or -1 if $\sum_{j=1}^P \lambda_j x_j^i \leq -\lambda_0$. The optimal threshold λ_0^* is an output because λ_0 is a decision variable in our model. Its value need not be decided before implementation unlike methods reliant on potentially sub-optimal predetermined thresholds, like logistic regression (Agarwal et al. 2019).

2.3. Rawlsian Loss Function

Our novel Rawlsian loss function minimizes classification error for the worst-off group.

$$\min_{\lambda \in \mathcal{X}^{P+1}} \left\{ \max_{k \in [K]} \left\{ \frac{1}{N_k} \sum_{i=1}^{N_k} \mathbf{1}\{y_{k(i)}(x^{k(i)})^T \lambda \leq 0\} + C_0 \|\lambda\|_0 + C_1 \|\lambda\|_1 \right\} \right\} \quad (4)$$

$[K]$ represents the index set of demographic groups $\{1, \dots, K\}$. N_k represents the number of data entries for demographic group k . $k(i)$ represents the i^{th} entry within the k^{th} group. Therefore, (4) is equivalent to minimizing the classification error rate (the proportion of misclassified individuals) for the worst-off demographic group. (4) can be thought of as a robust optimization problem because it has an outer-minimization objective paired with an inner-maximization objective (Ben-Tal and Nemirovski 2002). It is difficult to solve because the inner-maximization objective is nonlinear, and it is optimized over a discrete support. Therefore, duality methods, which are commonly applied to reformulate robust optimization problems, cannot be applied. To solve (4), we reformulate it as a MIP, which we present below in Section 2.4.

2.4. MIP Reformulation

We first introduce a MIP (5)-(9) that represents an equivalent formulation for the original loss function (1), which is the inner-minimization problem of (4) by introducing auxiliary variables α, β and γ , where $\alpha_i = \mathbf{1}\{y_i \neq \hat{y}_i\}$, $\beta_j = \mathbf{1}\{\lambda_j \neq 0\}$, and $\gamma_j = |\lambda_j|$ (Ustun et al. 2013).

$$\min_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \lambda} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i + C_0 \sum_{j=1}^P \beta_j + C_1 \sum_{j=1}^P \gamma_j \quad (5)$$

$$-M\alpha_i + \epsilon \leq y_i(x^i)^T \lambda \leq M(1 - \alpha_i) + \epsilon \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (6)$$

$$-\Lambda\beta_j \leq \lambda_j \leq \Lambda\beta_j \quad j = 1, \dots, P \quad (7)$$

$$-\gamma_j \leq \lambda_j \leq \gamma_j \quad j = 1, \dots, P \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha \in \{0, 1\}^N, \beta \in \{0, 1\}^P, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}_+^P, \lambda \in \mathcal{X} \quad (9)$$

(5) minimizes the average incorrect predictions plus zero and one norm penalty terms. (6) assigns the auxiliary variable α_i to 0 or 1 if the prediction is correct or incorrect, respectively. (7) and (8) equates β and γ to the L_0 and L_1 norm, respectively. Next, we introduce our novel formulation (10)-(15), which combines the MIP (5)-(9) with the Rawlsian fairness objective (4):

$$\min_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \lambda, \theta} \theta + C_0 \sum_{j=1}^P \beta_j + C_1 \sum_{j=1}^P \gamma_j \quad (10)$$

$$\theta \geq \frac{1}{N_k} \sum_{i=1}^{N_k} \alpha_{k(i)} \quad \forall k = 1, \dots, K, i = 1, \dots, N_k \quad (11)$$

$$-M\alpha_i + \epsilon \leq y_{k(i)}(x^{k(i)})^T \lambda \leq M(1 - \alpha_{k(i)}) + \epsilon \quad \forall k = 1, \dots, K, i = 1, \dots, N_k \quad (12)$$

$$-\Lambda\beta_j \leq \lambda_j \leq \Lambda\beta_j \quad j = 1, \dots, P \quad (13)$$

$$-\gamma_j \leq \lambda_j \leq \gamma_j \quad j = 1, \dots, P \quad (14)$$

$$\alpha \in \{0, 1\}^N, \beta \in \{0, 1\}^P, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}_+^P, \lambda \in \mathcal{X} \quad (15)$$

We introduce the decision variable θ to measure fairness. θ is the classification error rate for the worst-off demographic group, and its value is facilitated by constraint (11), which allows us to eliminate the min-max objective in (4) and replace it with a single linear minimization objective. The resulting problem (10)-(15) is a MIP that can be solved by off-the-shelf solvers.

Using a MIP provides the user flexibility to customize the model based on their preferences. For example, we can achieve the optimal balance between sparsity and error as in Ustun et al. (2013) by tuning the values of C_0 and C_1 . We also have the ability to add upper-bounding constraints to impose sparsity restrictions more strictly. We discuss this concept further in Section 3.2. Additionally, λ can be limited to only integer values, which could further improve interpretability.

3. Experimental Results

We perform several experiments to highlight the advantages of our model. We test our method on two datasets and demonstrate its ability to improve performance for the worst-off group without sacrificing overall performance, while being flexible and interpretable. We compare our method to two different well-cited fair classification approaches, Hardt et al. (2016) and Agarwal et al. (2018), to demonstrate its robustness across different established techniques. We conclude this section by comparing our model to other Rawlsian fairness approaches in the literature. Unless stated otherwise, experiments use $\epsilon = 0.1$, $\Gamma = 1000000$, $C_0 = C_1 = 0$, $M = 100$, and λ can be any real-valued vector. We use Gurobi to solve the model on a 1.6 GHz Dual-Core Intel Core i5 processor.

3.1. Penguin Dataset

The first dataset we consider is the Penguin Dataset from Horst et al. (2020), which contains 344 instances of penguins, and the classification task is to determine if each individual's species is Adelie, Gentoo, or Chinstrap. The data includes information on the penguins' bill length, bill depth, flipper length, body mass, and the year the data was collected. The demographic group we consider is the penguin's gender. We compare our Rawlsian MIP performance to the standard MIP approach used in Ustun et al. (2013), which does not consider fairness. For the training phase, we obtain an optimal λ^* by implementing the MIP (5)-(9) for the case without fairness considerations and (10)-(15) for our Rawlsian MIP on half of the dataset. Then, in the testing phase, we use this λ^* to classify the second half of the data. Since our formulation only performs binary classification, we perform three separate experiments, where the classification task for Experiments 1, 2, and 3 is to determine whether a penguin's species is Adelie or not-Adelie, Gentoo or not-Gentoo, and Chinstrap or not-Chinstrap, respectively. We present these results below in Table 1.

Table 1 Model comparison with Penguin Dataset

Exp.	MIP error (%)	Rawls error (%)	MIP fairness (%)	Rawls fairness (%)
1	1.75	1.17	3.49 (M)	2.53 (F)
2	1.17	1.17	3.27 (F)	3.27 (F)
3	4.09	3.51	4.65 (M)	3.80 (F)

We compare the error and the fairness of our Rawlsian fairness method and the MIP method that does not consider fairness. We define error as the proportion of incorrect classifications, and fairness is defined as the highest error across all demographic groups, which is the same fairness definition used in Hashimoto et al. (2018), Shah et al. (2021), Lahoti et al. (2020), and Martinez et al. (2021). For example, if a dataset contained 2 females and 8 males for a total of 10 individuals, and it incorrectly classified 1 female and 2 males, the error would be $\frac{1+2}{10} = 0.3$ and the fairness would be $\max\{\frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{8}\} = 0.5$. Furthermore, in these results, we indicate (M) or (F) to indicate whether the male or female group, respectively, is the worst-off group for the particular instance. In all experiments, both methods had perfect accuracy during the training phase so we only present results from the testing phase in Table 1. The two methods achieve the same performance in Experiment 2, but our Rawlsian MIP method improves both metrics in Experiments 1 and 3 compared to the standard MIP method. These results show that our methodology can improve accuracy for the worst-off group while additionally improving overall accuracy.

Figure 1 Fairness for different penalization values

3.2. Law Student Dataset

Next, we consider the Law Student Dataset (Wightman 1998). A detailed description of the dataset and access to the dataset itself is provided by Le Quy et al. (2022). It contains 20,798 entries from 163 law schools in the United States in 1991. Because of its size, we cannot solve the MIP to optimality given our available computational resources, so the results we present represent the best solution obtained after one hour of runtime. Despite this, our results still outperform other fair classification algorithms, which we discuss in Section 3.3.

The classification task is to predict whether students will pass the bar exam or not. We consider 9 features that describe attributes like GPA or LSAT score. This dataset is unbalanced, unlike the Penguin Dataset, which had nearly identical counts of males and females. The majority and minority races consist of 93% and 7% of the dataset, respectively in the Law Student Dataset, which can cause the minority group to be ignored by classification algorithms that do not consider fairness. For the remainder of Section 3.2, we first explore the relationship between model performance and sparsity before comparing our method to the standard MIP approach that doesn't consider fairness.

3.2.1. Sparsity via Penalization We compare our model performance for different values of C_0 and C_1 . We considered values of C_0 ranging from 0 to 0.0175, with $C_1 = 0$ and $C_1 = 0.001$. To further encourage sparsity in our solution, we set $\mathcal{X} = \mathbb{Z}^{P+1}$ (λ must be an integer vector). We evaluated the fairness produced by our model as the error for the worst-off demographic group, and we recorded this metric for the testing and training phases, as well as the overall performance (the average of the testing and training results). These results are shown in Figure 1.

As an overall trend, as C_0 increases, the error for the worst-off group increases. This indicates that higher C_0 values worsen our methodology's ability to enhance fairness. We can also observe that the overall fairness is worse when C_1 is increased from 0 to 0.001 for all values of C_0 . Increasing C_0 and C_1 encourages the model to produce sparser solutions that have fewer non-zero coefficients, which ultimately improves interpretability. However, the results in Figure 1 indicate that increasing these penalization terms worsens the fairness of the model's output. These results demonstrate a trade-off between sparsity and fairness. However, we provide an alternative method to induce sparsity without sacrificing fairness, which we introduce next.

3.2.2. Sparsity via Upper-bounding To further increase sparsity and interpretability, we add a constraint that was not considered in Ustun et al. (2013):

$$\sum_i^N \beta_i \leq b \tag{16}$$

Figure 2 Fairness for different upper-bound parameter values**Table 2** Error and fairness when $b = 5$ and $\lambda \in \mathbb{Z}^{P+1}$

	training error(%)	training fairness(%)	testing error(%)	testing fairness(%)
MIP	8.90	27.54	9.27	31.30
Rawlsian	9.30	26.23	9.07	26.73

(16) upper-bounds the decision variable β by a parameter b . This is ultimately a stronger way to reduce the size of the L_0 norm by introducing a hard constraint rather than using a penalization term in the objective function. We evaluated our model's performance for different values of b ranging from 3 to 7, and we considered the case where λ is restricted to real and integer values (Figure 2). Similarly to the results in Figure 1, we recorded the testing, training, and overall fairness, which we measure as the error for the worst-off group.

While the focus of this analysis is the relationship between fairness and the different ways to incorporate sparsity, we provide a brief example to illustrate how incorporating sparsity affects the optimal solutions. When sparsity was not considered ($C_0 = C_1 = 0$ and $b = \infty$), the optimal solution is $\lambda^* = [43.95, -1.56, -1.77, 0.28, -5.00, 3.77, 19.08, -5.29, -2.53, 3.70]$. Increasing C_1 to 0.005 yielded $\lambda^* = \frac{1}{100}[-45.71, -52.79, 73.98, 15.57, -0.18, 135.28, 13.26, 278.12, -7.02, 31.01]$. This caused the absolute values of the components of λ^* to decrease by roughly a factor of 3. Then, increasing C_0 to 0.005 yielded a solution where $\lambda_4^* = 0.00714$ and $\lambda_i^* = 0$ for all $i \neq 4$. Increasing the penalty for L_0 sparsity caused the amount of non-zero terms in λ^* to decrease to 1. We next observe the impacts of (16) in the integer case. Setting $C_0 = C_1 = 0$ and $b = 8$, $\lambda^* = [-30, 2, -, 1, -1, 3, 4, 0, 1, 2]$ and with $b = 5$ we get $\lambda^* = [-37, 0, 2, 1, 0, 0, 5, 0, 0, 3]$. Decreasing b from 8 to 5 forces optimal solution's number of non-zero entries down from 8 to 5.

When λ is allowed to be real-valued, $b = 5$ yielded the best fairness. When λ was forced to be integer, $b = 5$ also yielded the best fairness, and an even better fairness outcome than in the real case. Considering integer values provides a more interpretable solution, but it also improves performance in this case. Moreover, the case when $b = 5$ and λ is integer yielded the better fairness result in all of the results shown in Figure 1 when $C_0 > 0$ or $C_1 > 0$. This indicates using (16) induces sparsity without sacrificing fairness to the extent that using the penalization terms C_0 and C_1 does.

When b is increased to 6, the training performance improves because (16) is relaxed so the MIP can find a better solution in the training phase. However, this results in a worse overall performance, which indicates overfitting. On the other hand, as b is decreased to 3 or 4, the training performance also worsens because (16) becomes tighter and the testing performance also suffers. Furthermore, we can observe that the model performs better when λ is restricted to be an integer across all values of b . If λ^* is an integer vector, this could produce a cleaner result that is easier for decision-makers to implement in practical settings, such as the ones in Guskey (2013) or Knaus et al. (1991).

Table 3 Comparison with Hardt et al. (2016)

method	train error (%)	train fairness (%)	test error (%)	test fairness (%)
Rawlsian MIP	9.30	26.23	9.07	26.73
randomized threshold with AS	9.42	34.92	9.70	36.04
randomized threshold with BAS	22.92	27.38	24.25	29.10

We compare our Rawlsian MIP method to the standard MIP formulation in Ustun et al. (2013) that does not consider fairness. In training, our Rawlsian MIP does less than 1% worse concerning error, but it does a little more than 1% better for fairness compared to the MIP. During testing, our Rawlsian MIP performs slightly better (less than 1%) concerning error, but is 5% better for fairness compared to the MIP. If we consider the overall performance (average of testing and training), our Rawlsian method improves fairness by more than 3%, while increasing prediction error by only 0.1%. The standard MIP overlooks the minority group, which only accounts for 7% of the data, whereas our method is unaffected by the unbalanced data.

In summary, our MIP gives us flexibility to improve sparsity with an upper bounding constraint (16), and penalty terms C_0 and C_1 . Our empirical results show that (16) allowed us to increase sparsity without sacrificing model performance as much as utilizing penalty terms C_0 and C_1 did.

3.3. Model Comparisons

To ensure a rigorous and comprehensive evaluation, we compare our method to two different well-cited fairness approaches: Hardt et al. (2016) and Agarwal et al. (2018). Both of these methods are part of the open-source Fairlearn repository (Weerts et al. 2023), so their implementation is available and widely used, allowing for reproducible and transparent evaluation. In this section, we compare the results produced by these methods to the results obtained by our method from Table 2. These methods use demographic parity and equalized odds to evaluate fairness, which differs from our Rawlsian approach. These methods aim to ensure that accuracy across demographic groups is comparable, however, these fairness definitions have drawbacks. The first is that they can result in low prediction accuracy for the worst-off group since it is not directly prioritized. Another consequence of these fairness metrics is that they could sacrifice accuracy for non-worst-off groups to ensure similar performance to the worst-off group. We conclude this section by discussing other Rawlsian fairness methods and how they compare to ours.

3.3.1. Comparison to Randomized Threshold Approach First, we compare our results to the method proposed by Hardt et al. (2016). They use a randomized threshold to make classification predictions. It is designed to satisfy demographic parity or equalized odds. Demographic parity requires that a decision be independent of the demographic group, and equalized odds requires that the true and false positive rates are equal across demographic groups.

Our methodology differs from Hardt et al. (2016) in a few ways. Our method finds the optimal threshold value as opposed to a randomized sub-optimal threshold value used by Hardt et al. (2016). Furthermore, by using only one threshold, we can access similar information across different demographic groups, while using separate thresholds fails to capture this information. Moreover, they use fairness metrics that enforce similar performance across different groups. This results in solutions that can fail to improve the worst-off group’s performance or unnecessarily hurts non-worst-off groups. We verified these properties empirically by testing the method from Hardt et al. (2016) with different combinations of utility functions and fairness constraints. We compare the results to our method’s results in Table 3.

We consider different combinations of classification objectives. We only present the results with demographic parity since this yielded the better results than equalized odds. We only consider

Table 4 Comparison with Agarwal et al. (2018)

method	train error (%)	train fairness (%)	test error (%)	test fairness (%)
Rawlsian MIP	9.30	26.23	9.07	26.73
best grid search result	8.82	27.38	9.18	29.27

accuracy score and balanced accuracy, which we denote as AS and BAS, respectively since they were the best performing objectives. When AS is considered, they achieve similar fairness to our method, but at the cost of fairness, which is worse by 8%. When BAS is considered, however, their overall error is worse by at least 12%. Rather than improving the worst-off group to achieve demographic parity or equalized odds, they worsen the performance of the non-worst-off groups, leading to an overall decrease in accuracy. The random threshold approach suffers from the fairness-accuracy tradeoff discussed in Menon and Williamson (2018), while our method improves the performance of the worst-off group without sacrificing overall accuracy.

3.3.2. Comparison to Grid Search Approach Agarwal et al. (2018) aims to minimize the empirical error with respect to some random classifier subject to demographic parity (which is defined in the same way as Hardt et al. (2016)) constraints. They use Lagrangian reformulation to formulate a saddle point problem, then use grid search as a way of smartly searching the feasible region. As a result of the grid search algorithm, their methodology can produce multiple solutions. In our testing, we produced 16 solutions with varying performance. For brevity, we only display the best outcome of the 16 solutions for comparison in Table 4.

The grid search approach allows the algorithm to produce multiple results which gives the user a variety of options to choose from. Even the best results in terms of prediction error from Table 4 are comparable to our results. However, we achieve better performance for the worst-off group than the best results produced by the grid search algorithm by roughly 3% in the testing phase. Our method is better can achieve comparable accuracy without sacrificing the minority group’s performance.

3.3.3. Comparison to Other Rawlsian Approaches There are a few methods that also consider Rawlsian fairness with binary classification. However, their methods are incomparable to ours for numerous reasons. Hashimoto et al. (2018) considers a similar loss function, but they consider a dynamic setting that requires their model to be solved sequentially, whereas we consider a static case where the model needs to only be solved once. Lahoti et al. (2020) and Li et al. (2025) assume that the demographic group that each individual belongs to is unknown, which is different than the setting we consider. Martinez et al. (2021) produce results that are comparable to ours on the same Law Student Dataset. However, they make assumptions on the minimum “partition density”, which corresponds to the proportion a certain group makes up in the dataset. Our method makes no such assumption on the structure of the data, so it is more generalizable. Shah et al. (2021) requires second-order statistics of the underlying distribution, whereas our method does not require this information, so it can be used in more general settings. Nagpal et al. (2025) use a minimax objective and consider fairness. However, they consider demographic parity as their fairness metric, which we do not.

4. Conclusion

We proposed a novel Rawlsian MIP formulation to address the fair classification problem. Our Rawlsian fairness method allowed our model to prioritize the worst-off demographic group’s performance without unnecessarily harming other groups. The MIP framework outputs a single optimal threshold, which relieves the user from selecting a threshold value before implementing the model. Our MIP provides flexibility by allowing the user to adjust sparsity through penalization

in the objective or with upper-bounding constraints and offers flexibility to obtain real or integer coefficients based on domain-based preferences.

We tested our methodology on two datasets. Our experimental results displayed our Rawlsian MIP's ability to prioritize the performance of the worst-off group while still maintaining a high classification accuracy overall, even when performed on an unbalanced dataset. We also showcased the flexibility of our method in its ability to adjust the sparsity and interpretability of the results. Furthermore, we showed how our Rawlsian approach outperforms the alternative fairness methods incorporated in Hardt et al. (2016) and Agarwal et al. (2018), and discussed how our method compares to other Rawlsian fairness approaches.

Future directions include considering a multi-objective approach, where the model can simultaneously optimize worst-off performance with other objectives like overall error. Algorithmic improvements, such as cutting-plane heuristics, can improve our methodology's performance and allow for faster convergence. Finally, we can extend our framework to handle multiple classes.

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